

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Nanosponges: A New Generation of Nanoporous Materials for Biomedical Application

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 28 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

Nanosponges, Generation of Nanoporous, Materials for Biomedical Application.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14565645

ABSTRACT

Recent advances in nanotechnology demonstrate the increased attention that is now being turned to the supra molecular assembly of simple components for therapeutic and diagnostic purposes. This review contains detail about materials used in synthesis of Nano sponges, different methods of preparation, characterization and applications. Targeted and regulated drug delivery for both topical and oral application is made possible by an inventive and evolving technology known as a Nano sponge. In the pursuit of directing the drug to the required site of action, nanoparticle-based drug delivery systems, such as Nano sponge delivery, are essential. They enhance stability, reduce side effects and modify drug release. Nano sponge formulations involve encapsulation of drugs in a polymeric material and thus provide patient compliance, controlled site-specific drug release, increased formulation efficacy, improved stability and drug dosing. The drugs which have low solubility will be delivered to the site using the Nano sponge formulations with enhanced solubility and increased bioavailability, Nano sponge tablets assist cure conditions like cancer, diabetes mellitus, inflammation, and more. It also contains the new methodology and various formulations that were created recently from various categories of drug to treat the condition related to any disease with improving efficacy of that drug.

INTRODUCTION

Target-oriented medicine administration, increases in therapeutic efficacy, a decline in side effects, and better dosing regimens are the main trends in the therapeutics sector. Drug delivery systems based on nanoparticles, such as Nano sponge delivery, are crucial in delivering the

medication to the intended site of action. Initially, Nano sponges were developed for the topical delivery of drugs with a typical cross-sectional area of less than 1 μm . These gentle wipes can move throughout the body until they come into contact with the specific target region, adhere briefly, and begin to release the medication in a

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

predictable and controlled manner. A variety of materials can be found within Nano sponges, which are minute structures that resemble meshes (Figure a). Their spherical colloidal nature has been demonstrated, and because of their inclusion and non-inclusion properties, they are believed to have a significant ability to solubilize poorly soluble medications. Nano sponges have been developed and proposed recently for the delivery of pharmaceuticals. In addition to providing longer release and improving the bioavailability of drugs, Nano sponges can solubilize poorly water-soluble

pharmaceuticals. The size of Nano sponge ranges from 50 nm to 100 nm, with an average diameter of less than 4 μ m. This technique is used in prescription drugs, sunscreens, cosmetics, and over-the-counter skin care products. Traditional methods of topical pharmaceutical preparation cause significant accumulation in the dermis and epidermis. Nano sponges eliminate the active not accumulating in the dermis and epidermis. With Nano sponge technology, the irritation caused by the effective medicine is reduced without sacrificing.

Fig. a. (Formulation and development of Nano sponge)

History

Year	Orignie	Scientist	Material Nano Sponges	ReferEnce
1960-1980	Early Beginnings	Solms and Egli	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Porous material Microencapsulationn 	5
1990-2000	Nanotechnology Emergence		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nanoparticle • Dendrimers Nano porousmaterials 	6
2000-2010	Nano sponges Concept	Min Ma and De Quan Li	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First Nano sponge's synthesis (2003) • Biomedical application (2005) Environmental application (2008) 	7-8
2010-2011	Recent Advancement	Trotta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hybrid Nano sponges (2010) • Stimuli-responsive Nano sponges (2012) • Biodegradable Nano sponges 	9

			(2015) Large scale Nano sponges (2018)	
2011-2018	Notable Milestones	Cavalli	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FDA approval (2011) Commercialization (2015) International collaboration (2018)	10
Present	Future Direction		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personalized medicine Advanced biomaterials Energy storage and conversion Space exploration	11

DISADVANTAGES ^[15,16]

- Nanosponges have the capacity of encapsulating small molecules, not suitable for larger molecules.
- Dose dumping may occur at times.
- The particulate nature of NSs designed for topical use and the inconvenience associated with their direct application over the skin, are significant limitations.
- The loading ability of NSs rests on degree of crystallization.

Ideal Characteristics ^[17,20]

Composition Of Nanosponges ^[21,26]

1. Polymers
2. Cross linking agents
3. Drug molecules

1. Polymers

The kind of polymer has an impact on the production and performance of the Nano sponges. The size of the Nano sponges' cavities determines how much medicine they can hold. The polymer's ability to crosslink is determined by the substitution of functional and active groups. The following list includes some suitable instances of the polymers used in the formulation. Hyper cross-linked polystyrenes, cyclodextrins and their derivatives, including methyl β -cyclodextrin, alkyloxy-carbonyl cyclodextrins, 2-hydroxy propyl β -cyclodextrins, copolymers, including poly (Valero lactone–allyl Valero lactone) and poly (Valero lactone oxepanedione), cellulose, and

polyvinyl vinyl acetate (PVA) are samples of these materials. The required release and the properties of the drug molecule determine the polymer selection. The polymer must attach to the appropriate ligands for targeted drug release.

2. Cross linker

The type of polymer and the medicinal molecule that has to be formulated determine which crosslinking agents should be used. Carbonyl Di-imidazole, Diphenyl carbonate, Epichloridrine, Glutardehyde, Carboxylic acid di anhydrides, Di-arylcarbonates, Di-Isocyanates, Pyromellitic anhydride, Carbonyl Di-imidazoles, Epichloridrine, Glutraldehyde, Carboxylic acid dianhydrides, 2, 2-bisacrylamides are the crosslinking agents used in the production of nanosponges.

3. Drug molecules

Drug molecules used in the nanosponges should have the following characteristics

- Molecular weight should be in the range of 100-400 Daltons.
- It should consist less than five condensed rings.
- Melting point should below 250 °C.
- Solubility in water is less than 10ml.

Types Of Nanosponges [27]

Recent Advancement in Nanosponges

Name Of Formulations	Name Of Drug	Year	Reference
Oral drug formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Griseofulvin nanosponges • Metformin HCl nanosponges • Ketoconazole nanosponges • Atorvastatin calcium nanosponges • Quercetin nanosponges • Ibuprofen nanosponges 	2010 - 2018	28-33
Transdermal drug formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nicotine Nano sponge patches • Fentanyl Nano sponge patches • Insulin Nano sponge patches 	2012- 2019	34
Ocular drug formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timolol maleate nanosponges • Moxifloxacin nanosponges 	2013 - 2016	35
Injectable drug formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paclitaxel Nano sponge suspension • Doxorubicin Nano sponge liposomes 	2014 - 2017	36

Other drug formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curcumin nanosponges • Resveratrol nanosponges 	2018 - 2019	37
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Recent Work on Nanosponges

Sr. No	Name of Treatment	Category of Drug	Name of Drug	Action	Uses	Reference
1	Cancer Treatment	Anthracycline antibiotic Taxane	Doxorubicin Paclitaxel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Targeted delivery to cancer cells ▪ Enhanced solubility and bioavailability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Breast, lung, and liver cancer treatment ▪ Ovarian, breast, and lung cancer treatment 	38-39
2	Antibiotics	Fluoroquinolone	Ciprofloxacin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enhanced antibacterial activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Urinary tract infections ▪ Respiratory tract infections 	40
3	Anti-Inflammatory	NSAID	Ibuprofen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved bioavailability and reduced gastrointestinal side effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Pain relief, fever reduction 	41
4	Neurological Disorders	Acetylcholinesterase inhibitor	Rivastigmine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improved cognitive function in Alzheimer's disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Alzheimer's disease treatment 	42
5	Cardiovascular Diseases	Statin	Atorvastatin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Enhanced bioavailability and reduced side effects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cholesterol reduction ▪ cardiovascular disease prevention 	43
6	Other Applications	Peptide hormone Fat-soluble vitamin	Insulin Vitamin D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Oral delivery and improved bioavailability ▪ Enhanced bioavailability and improved bone health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Diabetes management ▪ Bone health, immune system support 	44 -45

Method Of Preparation Of Nanosponges ^[46-53]

1. Melt method

2. Emulsion Solvent Diffusion Method

Fig No. 2

3. Ultra sound Assisted Synthesis

4. Loading of Drug into Nano sponges

5. Quasi-Emulsion Solvent Diffusion

It is also possible to manufacture the Nano sponges using the quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion process with particular quantities of polymer. Eudragit RS100 was made into the organic phase by dissolving it in the appropriate solvent. The medication is mixed with the solution, and the

mixture gets heated to 35°C using ultra sonication. After swirling in water for an hour, the organic phase and the outer phase, or PVA solution, are merged. After that, the Nano sponges are filtered out of the mixture. An air-heated oven set to 40°C is used to dry the Nano sponges for 12 hours.

Fig No. 4

6. Nano sponges prepared from hyper cross linked cyclodextrin

In this strategy, cyclodextrin reacts with a cross-linker, like carbonyl diimidazoles, diaryl carbonates, or di-isocyanates. When it comes to how successfully the Nano sponges bind to other molecules, their size is determined by their porosity, or surface charge density. It will be

determined by the type of cross linker used whether the Nano sponges are acidic or neutral. The ability to encapsulate drugs with various shapes and solubility's using Nano sponges. In particular, BCS class II pharmaceuticals use them to improve the aqueous solubility of poorly water-soluble medicines.

Sr. No	Name Of Nano Sponges	Chemical Constituents	Properties Of Nano Sponges	Reference
1	CD-based ether NSs	Epichlorohydrin, bisphenol A diglycidyl ether, ethylene glycol diglycidyl ether, 1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether, E-51 epoxy resin	A high level of chemical resistance variable swelling ability	23
2	CD-based carbonate NS	1,1'- Carbonyl Diimidazole, diphosgene, Dimethyl carbonate, and Diphenyl carbonate	Less prone to swelling Stable in mildly alkaline and acidic liquids Small surface area	23
3	CD-based ester NSs	dianhydrides, Epiclon-B-4400; citric acid, and 2,6-naphthalene dicarboxylic acid (NDCA)	Easily hydrolyzed in aqueous media	24
4	CD-based urethane/ carbamate NSs	Di isocyanates like, methylene diphenyl diisocyanate	A rigid structure, Resistant to chemical deterioration Negligible swelling	25

New Methodology for The Preparation of Nanosponges^[54,55]

1. Electrospinning Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses electrostatic forces to create nanofibers • Can produce nanosponges with high surface area and porosity • Suitable for biopolymer-based nanosponges
2. 3D Printing Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses additive manufacturing to create complex nanosponge structures • Allows for precise control over pore size and shape • Suitable for ceramic and polymer-based nanosponges
3. Microfluidic Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses microfluidic channels to create nanoscale emulsions • Can produce nanosponges with uniform size and shape • Suitable for lipophilic and hydrophilic nanosponges
4. Supercritical Fluid Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses high-pressure CO₂ to create nanoscale particles • Can produce nanosponges with high purity and uniformity • Suitable for polymer and ceramic-based nanosponges
5. Sol-Gel Method with Ultrasonic Irradiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses ultrasonic waves to enhance sol-gel reaction • Can produce nanosponges with high surface area and porosity • Suitable for silica and metal oxide-based nanosponges
6. Nanoprecipitation Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses solvent displacement to create nanoscale particles • Can produce nanosponges with high loading capacity • Suitable for polymer and lipophilic nanosponges
7. Laser-Based Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses laser ablation to create nanoscale particles • Can produce nanosponges with high purity and uniformity • Suitable for metal and metal oxide-based nanosponges
8. Hybrid Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combines multiple methods to create nanosponges with unique properties • Can produce nanosponges with high performance and functionality • Suitable for various applications.
9. Microemulsion Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses microemulsions to create nanoscale particles • Can produce nanosponges with high surface area and porosity • Suitable for lipophilic and hydrophilic nanosponges

Nano Sponge Formulation Advantages

Nano Sponge Formulation Disadvantages

Nanosponge Limitations

Physical Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Aggregation and settling ➤ Instability in aqueous environments ➤ Limited shelf-life due to moisture sensitivity ➤ Potential for oxidation or photo degradation ➤ Difficulty in achieving consistent particle size and distribution
Chemical Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Limited chemical stability ➤ Potential for degradation or hydrolysis ➤ Incompatibility with certain drugs or excipients ➤ Limited solubility in certain solvents ➤ Potential for chemical interactions with biological molecules
Biological Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Potential for cytotoxicity or genotoxicity ➤ Inflammation or immune response ➤ Biodegradation products may be toxic ➤ Uncertainty surrounding long-term biocompatibility ➤ Potential for accumulation in organs or tissues
Pharmacological Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Unpredictable pharmacokinetics ➤ Potential for altered bio distribution ➤ Limited understanding of pharmacodynamics ➤ Difficulty in optimizing dosing regimens ➤ Potential for drug-drug interactions
Toxicological Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Potential for toxicity due to nanoscale size ➤ Uncertainty surrounding chronic toxicity ➤ Limited understanding of environmental impact ➤ Potential for bioaccumulation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Challenges in ensuring safe handling and disposal
Regulatory Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ ➤ Limited guidance on Nano sponge regulations ➤ Uncertainty surrounding regulatory classification ➤ High costs associated with regulatory compliance ➤ Potential for lengthy approval processes ➤ Limited standardization in Nano sponge characterization
Scalability Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Difficulty in scaling up production ➤ High manufacturing costs ➤ Limited availability of cGMP facilities ➤ Potential for contamination or batch failures ➤ Challenges in ensuring reproducibility
Economic Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ ➤ High development costs ➤ Limited market demand or competition ➤ Potential for patent disputes ➤ Challenges in securing funding or investment ➤ Uncertainty surrounding reimbursement policies
Environmental Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Potential for environmental contamination ➤ Uncertainty surrounding Nano sponge degradation ➤ Limited understanding of ecological impact ➤ Potential for bioaccumulation ➤ Challenges in ensuring sustainable production

Nanosponge Marketed Formulation

Type Of Formulation	Name Of Formulation	Uses
Pharmaceuticals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Abraham ▪ Doxia ▪ Amboise ▪ Paclitaxel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Breast cancer treatment ▪ Cancer treatment ▪ Fungal infection treatment ▪ Breast cancer treatment
Cosmetics and Skincare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Neutrogena's Hydro Boost Water Gel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Moisturizing cream

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ L'Oréal's Revivalist ▪ Nivea's Q10 Plus ▪ La Roche 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Anti-aging cream ▪ Anti-aging cream ▪ Posey's Tolerance Ultra Fluid
Medical Devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 3M's Tegaderm Nano sponge Dressing ▪ Johnson & Johnson's Bio absorbable Nano sponge Scaffold ▪ Medtronic's Nano sponge-based Wound Dressing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Wound care ▪ Tissue engineering ▪ Wound care
Food and Nutrition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nestlé's Nano sponge-based Food Packaging ▪ Danone's Nano sponge-based Probiotic Delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Food preservation ▪ Probiotic supplements
Other Marketed Products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ BASF's Nano sponge-based Water Purification System ▪ 3M's Nano sponge-based Air Purification System 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Water treatment ▪ Air filtration

Patents

US Patents	International Patents	Patent Assignees	Patent Categories	Recent Patent Filings
1. US 9,011,881 (2015): "Nano sponge" - A New Class of Organic-Inorganic Hybrid Materials 2. US 10,456,91(2019): "Mesoporous Silica Nano sponge-Based Drug Delivery Systems" 3. US 9,435,949 (2016): "Titanium Dioxide Nano sponges for Biomedical Applications"	1. WO 2018/075,331 (2018): "Nano sponge-Based System for Delivery of Therapeutic Agents" 2. EP 3,443,191 (2019): "Mesoporous Silica Nano sponges for Biomedical Applications" 3. CN 109,531,442 (2019): "Titanium Dioxide Nano	1. University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA) 2. Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) 3. Harvard University 4. 3M 5. Johnson & Johnson 6. Merck 7. Pfizer 8. Sanofi 9. GlaxoSmithKline 10. Celgene	1. Biomedical applications (drug delivery, tissue engineering, wound healing) 2. Materials science (Nano sponge synthesis, characterization) 3. Pharmaceutical formulations (Nano sponge-based drug delivery systems) 4. Medical devices (wound	1. US2022/023,133 (2022): "Nano sponge-Based System for Delivery of RNA Therapeutics" 2. WO2022/075,211 (2022): "Silicon-Based Nano sponge Scaffolds for 3D Cell Culture"

<p>4. US 10,131,94(2018): "Silicon-Based Nano sponge Scaffolds for Tissue Engineering"</p> <p>5. US 9,949,072 "Nano sponge-Based Wound Dressing for Enhanced Wound Healing" (2018)</p>	<p>sponge-Based Biomedical Materials"</p>		<p>dressings, implants)</p> <p>5. Energy storage and conversion (Nano sponge-based electrodes)</p>	
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Factor Affecting Nanosponges ^[56,61]

1. Depending on property of crosslinked and polymer used

In order to create a three-dimensional structure, NSs need cross linkers. The form of a cross-link used helps determine the extent of drug immobilization and shapes organ targeting. It is determined by the type the crosslinked that is used whether the NS dissolves in water or another solvent. The objective is to crosslink with epichlorohydrin to produce hydrophilic NSs. The advantages of using hydrophobic NSs to deliver medications include better drug absorption via biological membranes and useful transport for medications in formulations meant for instant release. Water-hating NSs are made using crossovers that involve isocyanates, carbonyl imidazole's, pyromellitic anhydride (PVA), and DPC. Hydrophobic NSs are a continuous release medication delivery system for patients who prefer water.

2. Medium used to show interaction and the property of drug

A chemical must fulfil certain criteria in order to be approved for encapsulation and selected for integration into neural scaffolds (NSs). The pharmaceutical molecule's molecular mass should be within hundred and four hundred Da and less than five compacted rings. It is advised to keep the

solubility below 10 mg/ml within water and the melting point below 250 °C. Following capturing in NSs, compounds with melting points that are elevated demonstrate a lower stabilization constant value, which leads to the discovery of uneven complex within the drug and NSs. Additionally, drugs with high points of melting may not be as trapped, which will affect how much they can load. One important element influencing the pace of drug loading is the drug loading medium. Of medication release, since it helps the targeted chemical engage with the holes in the NSs. In a water-based medium, the organic substance molecule accumulates in the hydrophilic cavities of NSs; in a chemical solvent medium, the molecules of organic compounds are released from the NSs. Among both the host and the guest molecules, the magnitude of the attraction is determined by both physical and chemical forces.

3. The substitution degree for crosslinking

The number of substituents and the degree of polymerization are strongly related; more replacements might lead to a larger degree of cross linkage, which creates extremely porous NSs with internal mesh networking. Because the functional group occupies distinct places on the parent molecule, an adjustment in the production method could lead to a material with varied physicochemical properties. The final NSs value,

whose value depends on the manner of manufacture and material purity of the product, establishes the degree of polymer's importance.

4. Complexation nature

An increased degree of crosslinking caused by a greater amount of replacements can result in highly porous NSs with internal mesh networking. There is a substantial correlation between the amounts of substituents with the level of binding. Because each of the functional groups are positioned differently on the parent molecule, variations in the production process can result in a material with differing physicochemical properties. The final value of the NSs, which hinges on the product's processing and material purity, illustrates exactly how significant an amount of polymer substitution is.

Evaluation Parameters For Determination Of Nano Sponges Particle Size ^[62, 69]

During the polymerization process, the size of the particles can be controlled to produce free-flowing powders with exceptional aesthetic qualities. Using a Malvern Zeta sizer or laser light diffractometric, the particle sizes of loaded and unloaded Nano sponges will be investigated. Larger particles exceeding 30 m may give the application a gritty appearance, therefore particles between 10 and 25 m are most suited for usage in the finished topical formulation.

1. FTIR (Fourier transform infrared) analysis

In order to confirm whether a chemical bond connection between the medication and the polymer was possible, an infrared spectroscopy technique called Fourier transform was employed. By applying charcoal black as the reference, the materials were scanned in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ range. The signal and moisture content were both decreased.

2. Thin-Layer Chromatography

A drug molecule's *R_f* value significantly decreases in thin-layer chromatography, which aids in determining whether a complex involving

the drug with Nano sponges has formed. There is a reversible inclusion complexation between the living thing and visiting molecules. During the chromatographic process, the complex may thus fully split into the guest molecule and host molecules, leaving only their individual spots on the TLC plate.

3. Solubility studies

Among the methods used to assess a medication's solubility and bioavailability are inclusion complexes. The inclusion aggregates of Nano sponges are most frequently examined using this method. One can use the phase solubility plot to determine the degree of completion. Drugs' solubility is investigated through solubility experiments to determine their pH level, the dissolution profile, and contributory factor.

4. Determination of loading efficiency and production yield

The amount of drug not entrapped is subtracted from the total amount of drug to calculate the prepared Nano sponge loading efficiency. The effectiveness of drug entrapment will be evaluated by separating the untrapped substance using any appropriate analytical technique. the procedure that uses dialysis, gel filtration, and ultra-centrifugation to separate untrapped medicines. Effective amounts of drugs in Nano sponge is equal to loading efficiency.

5. Microscopic study

Under a microscope, medicines and Nano sponges can be examined using electron transmission microscopes and scanning electron microscopes. The production of inclusion complexes is demonstrated by the difference between the product seen under the microscope's light and the crystallization state.

6. Zeta potential determination

When two fluid layers are connected by dispersed particles, the immobile layer and the dispersion medium have different potentials, which is known as the zeta potential. The potential for zeta is the

most important and fundamental measure of the consistency of the colloidal dispersion. By putting an extra electrode or zeta separator in a particle size device, the potential of zeta can be found. Whenever this zeta potential value rises, the colloidal dispersion becomes more stable. Hydrogen bonding is done by the absorption bands, which often grow, shift to a lower frequency, and become stronger. The stretching vibration band moves most closely to the hydrogen bond of the hydroxyl group.

7. Infra-Red spectroscopy

The solid-state drug molecules' interaction with the Nano sponge is evaluated using infrared spectroscopy. Following the formation of a complex, Nano sponge band alterations are frequently quite minor. If the guest molecules make up less than 25% of the entire complex, the wavelengths of the Nano sponge spectrum readily cover any bands that would represent the guest molecules. Compared to alternative methods, the approach used is less revealing and frequently insufficient to identify the inclusion complexes. Drugs with specific bands, like sulfonyl or carbonyl groups, can only be evaluated via infrared spectroscopy. Using the infrared spectrum, one can examine how hydrogen behaves in different functional groups.

8. Thermo-analytical methods

To determine if the pharmaceutical substance changes in any manner before the Nano sponge

heats up, thermoanalytic techniques are employed. The drug material could oxidize, melt, evaporate, dissolve, or go through a polymorphic transition. The drug's evolving composition indicates the growth of the complex. Thermograms generated by The DTA and DSC can be examined for changes, such as peaks growing, shifting, or disappearing completely. Weight loss changes could indicate inclusion complexes.

9. Permeation studies

For the diffusion studies, which were carried out at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with 250 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as the dissolving media, a produced Nano sponge sample (0.5 g) can be put on a cellophane membrane. At 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 7 and 8 hours, five milliliters of each sample can be taken out and replaced with an equivalent amount of brand-new dissolving media.

10. Drug release kinetics

In order to explore the mechanism of releasing medications from the Nano sponge, the release data was evaluated using the simplest order, initial order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer-Peppas, Hixon Crowell, Koch, and Makoid-Banakar models. The data can be analysed with Graph Pad Prism program. The program determines which of several non-linear function parameters best fits the experimental data.

Application ^[65,70]

Silent Features

By varying the ratios of polymers to crosslinking agents, Nano sponges—which are composed of up of particles of a specific size—can be rendered polar or non-polar. Nano sponges range in void polarity and are less than 1 μm . There can be crystalline or para-crystalline forms. The crystallized form of Nano sponges plays a role for drug interaction because the degree of crystallization greatly affects how efficient it is of stackable Nano sponges. According to previous literature, Nano sponges or Para crystalline have been shown to have various kinds of drug-loading capabilities. They have been discovered to be stable between 1-11 °P and 130 °C. Nanoparticles have been discovered to be permeable, biodegradable, and non-toxic. Their three-dimensional structure allows them to transport, encapsulate, and release medications and other substances in an observable way. When water is added to Nano sponges, a clear to opalescent colloidal solution is created. This solution can be recovered by solvent distillation or through desorption with microwave and ultrasonic waves. Due to their ability to interact with several functional groups—which can be increased by employing synthetic linkers that specifically target specific sites—they indicate targeted release of numerous compounds. Magnetic fields from the outside can be used to target expelled by adding magnetic abilities to a Nano sponge configuration through the extension of ferromagnetic and other magnetic materials over the production process. The material preferred by consumers is nan sponges due to their many benefits, including as the capacity to deliver a substance's sustained release for as long as twenty-four hours. To encapsulate liquids that aren't soluble, providing increased flexibility, stability, and reduced excitability. Nan sponges supply a number of advantages but they also have some drawbacks. Although their bodies are suited to incorporating

macromolecules and oligonucleotides, the Nano sponges mostly incorporate small medicinal compounds. The quantity of crosslinking has a consequence on the ability to load drugs because it controls the amount of unoccupied space in the Nano sponge that is readily accessible for loading.

CONCLUSION

According to the previous study, Nano sponges, a novel type of drug delivery vehicles, offer controlled drug administration for topical application. These microscopic particles can carry polar and slimy substances, and they can also increase the dispersion of poorly soluble molecules. Their small particle size and spherical shape allow them to be produced in an assortment of delivery modes, including topical and oral parenteral dosage forms. In a controlled and predictable manner, the medication will emerge from Nano sponges. The Nano sponges provide site-specific drug delivery and longer dosage intervals. They work in many different industries, such as oil clean up, floriculture, and the food industry. They are shown to have a powerful ability to protect important biomarkers in a number of diseases, including as biocatalysts from cancer and physiochemical breakdown. Future developments in drug delivery methods will be greatly aided by Nano sponges.

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HOW TO CITE: Jayashri Dandale, Sadhana Shahi, Tejas Khatavkar, Shweta Patil, Nanosponges: A New Generation of Nanoporous Materials for Biomedical Application, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 3280-3301. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14565645>

